

Full Research Paper

The backbone and the bridges: Central influence and collaborative integration in Living Labs scholarship

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Abstract

Over the past two decades, Living Labs have gained significant traction in both academic and practitioner communities. While the concept has been applied across diverse domains, concerns persist about its theoretical coherence and structural fragmentation. This study investigates the intellectual landscape of Living Lab research through network analysis, with a focus on two key hypotheses: the Central Influence Hypothesis (H1) and the Collaborative Integration Hypothesis (H2). H1 posits that a small set of authors and seminal publications form the backbone of the field, exerting disproportionate influence on its development. H2 explores whether scholarly collaboration in the field is characterized by cohesive sub-networks or significant structural disjunctions that limit interdisciplinary integration. Using a dataset of 2,358 unique publications, we construct and analyse co-authorship networks to identify central figures, collaboration patterns, and gaps in scholarly cohesion. Findings reveal that while the field is anchored by a concentrated group of influential authors, it remains structurally fragmented, with low cross-cluster integration and limited knowledge exchange across disciplinary or geographic boundaries. These dynamics present both opportunities and risks for the future of Living Labs: while core communities provide stability and shared vocabulary, the lack of broader connectivity may hinder theoretical advancement and practical innovation. We conclude by outlining strategic implications for research and practice, advocating for more inclusive, interdisciplinary, and longitudinal approaches to consolidate and expand the Living Labs knowledge base.

Key words

Living Labs, network analysis, co-authorship, knowledge ecosystems, interdisciplinary collaboration, research fragmentation

Introduction

The evolution of Living Lab research can be situated within broader debates on knowledge accumulation in emerging fields. As Shafique (2013) argues, such fields oscillate between fragmentation and coherence, with paradigmatic works acting as anchors (Kuhn 1970). Similarly, Fagerberg et al. (2012) show that in innovation studies, intellectual "exemplars" stabilize otherwise fast-growing and diverse literatures. In the case of Living Labs, early foundational texts, such as Ballon, Pierson, and Delaere (2005) on methodological framing, or Bergvall-Kåreborn and Ståhlbröst (2009) on user involvement, serve this stabilizing role.

Yet, as Small (1973) first showed in co-citation analyses, emerging fields often develop fragmented peripheries where thematic clusters evolve in isolation. In Living Lab research, this manifests in the coexistence of relatively well-integrated clusters – urban sustainability (Bulkeley et al., 2016; Marvin et al., 2018), technological and digital innovation (Leminen & Westerlund, 2012; Schuurman, 2015) – alongside weakly connected domains such as health, ethics, and data privacy (Nyström et al., 2014). This aligns with Boyack and Klavans (2010) and Zupic and Čater (2015), who emphasize that coherence and fragmentation typically co-exist in emerging literatures.

This duality also appears in the distribution of scholarly influence. As de Solla Price (1965, 1976) and Lotka's Law demonstrate (Aytac, Tran & Frye 2025), scientific fields tend toward highly skewed citation distributions, where a small number of works dominate. Newman (2001) further shows that collaboration networks often display scale-free properties, reinforcing centralization. In Living Labs, seminal contributions, such as typologies of actors and processes (Leminen, Nyström & Westerlund, 2012, 2014; Schuurman, 2015), act as such hubs.

The collaborative structures of the field display similar tensions. Wagner and Leydesdorff (2005) note that international collaboration networks in emerging domains initially remain fragmented, while Leahey and Reikowsky (2008) highlight the difficulty of sustaining cross-disciplinary ties. Empirical evidence suggests that Living Lab research is marked by tightly knit clusters and structural gaps, rather than fully integrated communities (Frantzeskaki & Rok, 2018). The Quadruple/Quintuple Helix framework (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012) reinforces the idea that inclusive, cross-sector collaboration is essential for innovation ecosystems like Living Labs.

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Taken together, these insights suggest that the trajectory of Living Lab research mirrors broader patterns in the evolution of scientific fields. As Crossan and Apaydin (2010) and Callon et al. (1991) argue, maturity depends on circulation, recombination, and integration across networks. Mature knowledge networks tend to balance central authority with distributed connectivity (Wasserman & Faust, 1994; Gulati, Nohria & Zaheer, 2000; Provan & Kenis, 2008). While centralization provides stability, Powell et al. (2005) and Uzzi & Spiro (2005) caution that over-dependence on a few nodes can reduce resilience and stifle novelty. Distributed participation and redundancy are necessary for resilience (Borgatti & Halgin, 2011).

This study responds to the growing scholarly and practical interest in Living Labs, which has led to a proliferation of research themes and applications. While this expansion signals the concept's relevance, it also raises concerns about the fragmentation of the field. To evaluate the maturity and coherence of the academic field, this study investigates the intellectual structure of Living Lab research. Specifically, it addresses the guiding question: How is the intellectual landscape of Living Labs characterized, and who are the key authors and structural gaps that persist between its widespread use and its scholarly consolidation?

Our research agenda is guided by four hypotheses to assess the intellectual landscape of Living Labs and identify gaps between popular adoption and scholarly understanding. Two of these, the Conceptual Coherence Hypothesis and the Thematic Structure Hypothesis are treated extensively in Fierăscu and Schuurman (2025). That analysis reveals that the Living Lab literature is characterized by a robust conceptual core with fragmented edges. On the one hand, we find strong evidence of conceptual coherence: shared citations to seminal works in open and user innovation, as well as overlapping keywords, such as "innovation" and "co-creation", indicate a stable and interconnected knowledge base that anchors the field. Despite thematic diversity, the field maintains a recognizable backbone rooted in open innovation (Chesbrough, 2003), user innovation (von Hippel, 2005), and participatory design traditions (Schaffers et al., 2011).

On the other hand, certain specialized or emerging areas, such as data ethics, privacy, health outcomes, and long-term evaluation, remain weakly integrated into this discourse, suggesting that important concerns are still developing at the periphery. Some of these clusters, particularly those oriented toward practical implementation versus theoretical development, are not well integrated, and specific niches remain underrepresented. Taken together, these findings suggest a dual structure: a coherent and widely recognized intellectual core that provides the field with identity and stability, alongside parallel

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thematic streams that evolve in relative isolation, underscoring the need for stronger cross-fertilization and deeper theoretical integration in future research.

Building on these findings, the next step is to examine the forces that shape and sustain this intellectual landscape. This is where the Central Influence Hypothesis and the Collaborative Integration Hypothesis come into focus.

H1: The Central Influence Hypothesis: This hypothesis posits that a core group of seminal publications and key authors forms the backbone of the Living Lab literature, wielding a disproportionate influence on the field's discourse. If confirmed, this hypothesis would identify the most influential works and figures, highlighting areas of rigorous academic inquiry, while also revealing gaps in the deep theoretical understanding of the Living Lab concept.

H2: Collaborative Integration Hypothesis: This hypothesis suggests that the pattern of scholarly collaborations in Living Lab research is characterized by both tightly interconnected communities and significant disjunctions. These structural features, if found, would underscore the potential for interdisciplinary knowledge exchange while simultaneously pointing to gaps that may hinder the development of a unified, rigorous body of knowledge.

Intellectual coherence in emerging fields such as Living Labs may initially crystallize around a small number of influential works or scholars. These anchors provide stability and direction, giving the field its early identity. Yet the transition from coherence to maturity depends on the collaborative pathways that enable ideas to circulate, recombine, and evolve. Without distributed participation and cross-cluster integration, the field risks becoming overly dependent on a handful of nodes, limiting both resilience and innovation. A mature intellectual network, by contrast, is characterized by redundancy, distributed centrality, and diverse knowledge flows, ensuring that Living Labs can develop as a cohesive yet adaptive body of knowledge. By focusing on these hypotheses, we position our analysis to reveal both the consolidating mechanisms that strengthen the Living Lab literature and the structural gaps that future research communities will need to address to ensure its sustainable evolution.

Data and Methodology

To examine our hypotheses, we employed co-authorship network analysis, a method widely used in scientometrics to uncover the social structure of knowledge production (Newman, 2001; Glänzel & Schubert, 2004). In such networks, each author is represented as a node and co-authorship relations form the links, allowing us to visualize and measure how scholarly communities are organized.

To build a comprehensive picture of the literature on Living Labs, we began with a systematic search designed to capture both the breadth and depth of the field. Because Living Labs are a practitioner-driven phenomenon that often lies outside mainstream academic publishing, we first cast a wide net. A broad Google Scholar search for the terms "living lab" or "living labs" appearing anywhere in the text yielded more than 36,000 publications published up to the end of 2024. From this vast set, we then narrowed the focus to those works where Living Labs were not just mentioned in passing but treated as a central theme. To do this, we retained only those publications that explicitly listed "living lab(s)" as keywords, a filter that reduced the dataset to 8,920 publications, or about a quarter of the original pool.

From this point, our goal was to identify the most influential contributions that have shaped scholarly debates on Living Labs. We applied a citation threshold to highlight highly cited work across databases. On Google Scholar, this meant including publications with at least 200 citations, which yielded 39 core papers. To complement this set, we conducted a Scopus search for works that featured "living lab(s)" in their keywords and had received at least 50 citations, adding 19 further publications that were not captured by the Google Scholar results. Together, these steps produced a core corpus of 58 highly cited and Living Lab-focused publications, which we take to represent the backbone of scholarly knowledge in the field.

To better understand how this knowledge has developed and what intellectual traditions it draws upon, we extended the dataset to include all references cited within these 58 publications. This process generated a list of 6,241 cited works, representing **2,299 unique** titles drawn from 2,133 different sources such as journals, conferences, and books. Taken together, this dual dataset offers a rich foundation for our network analyses. It allows us to trace not only the key authors and works that structure the discourse, but also the collaborative and intellectual ties that connect the Living Lab community. As network theory suggests, knowledge does not advance through isolated contributions, but through embeddedness in wider structures of exchange (Borgatti et al., 2009).

To test the Central Influence Hypothesis (H1), we applied **standard centrality measures** to identify the authors who act as hubs, bridges, or leaders within the network. Central authors are not only prolific but often set the agenda for others, shaping which ideas become dominant (Freeman, 1979; Wasserman & Faust, 1994). For the Collaborative Integration Hypothesis (H2), we focused on the network's community structure. Detecting clusters reveals whether the field consists of tightly knit subgroups or a more integrated scholarly space (Girvan & Newman, 2002). The presence of a giant component – a large, connected cluster of authors – would indicate a broadly shared research space, while disconnected components would suggest persistent silos.

Compared to keyword or co-citation analyses, which map the intellectual structure of ideas, co-authorship networks expose the social infrastructure of research. This distinction matters: intellectual coherence may emerge from a small number of influential works, but whether the field matures into a cohesive body of knowledge depends on the collaborative pathways that allow ideas to circulate and evolve. By applying co-authorship analysis, we therefore gain a unique vantage point on how influence and integration are enacted through human collaboration, offering direct empirical traction on our two hypotheses.

Results

In exploring the intellectual space, we constructed the co-authorship network from the co-citation database.

Figure 1. Co-authorship network (nodes = authors, links = co-authored papers)

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The co-authorship network highlights how Living Lab research is driven by a handful of influential clusters, each organized around a few central authors. If the vocabularies we use and the knowledge base, we build on are more or less congruent, the co-authorship space is fragmented. Rather than a single, unified network, the graph reveals a patchwork of collaboration sub-networks. The level of intra-cluster collaboration varies, with some groups operating as tightly woven teams and others as more loosely affiliated researchers. Such a structure can foster innovation within each cluster but may also limit cross-pollination of ideas across the field unless additional "bridge" collaborations are formed.

Table 1. Co-authorship communities with their top 10 members

	Bulkeley, H	Raven, R	Schaffers, H	Schuurman, D	Leminen, S
1	Wirth, T	Heiskanen, E	Pallot, M	Ballon, P	Westerlund, M
2	Frantzeskaki, N	Schot, J	Komninos, N	Marez, L	Nystrom, A
3	Marvin, S	Smith, A	Trousse, B	Pierson, J	Hossain, M
4	Coenen, L	Kivimaa, P	Guzman, J	Baccarne, B	Coenen, T
5	Kronsell, A	Geels, F	Oliveira, A	Mechant, P	Kortelainen, M
6	Mukhtar-Landgren, D	Kemp, R	Budweg, S	Lievens, B	Veeckman, C
7	Mai, L	Weber, M	Senach, B	Vangenck, M	Gray, M
8	Palgan, Y	Turnheim, B	Scapin, D	Evens, T	Tsvetkova, A
9	Fuenfschilling, L	Grin, J	Nilsson, M	Jacobs, A	Moller, K
10	Hartmann, C	Torrens, J	Salminen, J	Logghe, S	Hellstrom, M
%GC	15%	12%	12%	10%	8%
Nodes	57	53	51	44	34
Edges	64	54	60	61	41
AvgWDegree	27	3	17	30	41
CCEmp	0.23	0	0.48	0.44	0.24
CCRand	0.013	0.012	0.036	0.034	0.036
Dif_f_Rand	18	0	13	13	7

Table 1 highlights a cluster-level snapshot of the Living Labs' intellectual network, showing the main author communities, their size, and structural properties. Bulkeley, Raven, Schaffers, Schuurman, Leminen are the cluster leaders, i.e. the most central authors within five distinct communities of research around Living Labs. Each column is essentially a "school of thought" or thematic subnetwork. The authors below are the main co-authors or collaborators orbiting around each cluster leader. For example, around Bulkeley we see names like Frantzeskaki, Marvin, Coenen, Kronsell, i.e. the sustainability transitions and urban governance cluster. Around Schaffers we see Komninos, Pallot, Trousse, more ICT/innovation/technical infrastructure oriented. Around Leminen we see

Westerlund, Nystrom, Kortelainen, the Finnish-led business model, innovation management, and ecosystem perspective.

- **%GC (Giant Component share)** → The proportion of the entire network that each cluster represents. Bulkeley's cluster accounts for 15% of the field, Raven and Schaffers 12% each, Schuurman 10%, Leminen 8%. Together, they cover over half the intellectual space.
- **Nodes** → Number of distinct authors in each cluster.
- **Edges** → Number of co-authorships within that cluster.
- **AvgWDeg (Average Weighted Degree)** → How dense and active the collaborations are. For example, Leminen's cluster is smaller, but very dense (AvgWDeg 41), while Raven's cluster is more fragmented (AvgWDeg 3).
- **CCEmp (Empirical Clustering Coefficient)** → How cohesive the cluster is internally (e.g., Schaffers' and Schuurman's clusters are tightly knit at ~0.44–0.48, Raven's is 0, meaning very fragmented).
- **CCRand (Random Graph Benchmark)** → The expected clustering if connections were random.
- **Dif_f_Rand** → How much higher the empirical clustering is compared to random. This highlights how non-random and "real" these communities are (Bulkeley +18, Schaffers +13, Schuurman +13). Raven's = 0, meaning his group is more of a loose constellation than a cohesive cluster.

The groups led by Schaffers and Schuurman show strong internal cohesion, with high clustering coefficients indicating frequent and recurrent collaboration. Leminen's smaller group stands out for its exceptionally high collaboration intensity, suggesting a highly active and productive research core.

Bulkeley's network, with 57 nodes and moderate clustering, shows structured and statistically significant collaboration, supporting steady knowledge exchange. In contrast, Raven's similarly sized network is sparse and poorly connected, with minimal internal collaboration, indicating a less cohesive and potentially less integrated research group.

The findings show that key researchers like Schaffers, Schuurman, and Leminen are part of dense, collaborative networks that shape the field, while others like Raven remain more isolated. These structural differences influence how ideas spread and evolve within Living Lab research (Velden, Haque & Lagoze 2010, Greve et al. 2021). Strengthening connections between fragmented groups is essential for advancing theoretical development and innovation. Events like Open Living Lab Days and infrastructures such

as Research Groups and Communities of Practice offer valuable opportunities to foster such collaboration and cohesion.

Based on the network analyses, the following authors play an integrative role in the intellectual space:

Table 1. Key author roles in the living labs intellectual space

Popular	Influential	Connector
Schaffers, H	Schaffers, H	Schaffers, H
Bulkeley, H	Mulder, I	Mulder, I
Schuurman, D	Puerari, E	Puerari, E
Frantzeskaki, N	Loorbach, D	Loorbach, D
Katzy, B	Frantzeskaki, N	Frantzeskaki, N
Mulder, I	McCormick, K	McCormick, K
Raven, R	Bulkeley, H	Bulkeley, H
Ballon, P	Nystrom, A	Nystrom, A
Pallot, M	Schuurman, D	Schuurman, D
Lievens, B	Pallot, M	Pallot, M

“Popular” authors have many direct co-authorships, indicating broad collaboration. “Influential” authors are central in the network, connecting with other highly connected scholars and shaping information flow. “Connectors” serve as bridges between otherwise disconnected groups, enabling knowledge exchange across research clusters.

The repeated appearance of certain names (e.g., Schaffers, Bulkeley, Schuurman, Frantzeskaki) across multiple columns signals that these individuals or teams likely set or significantly influence research agendas. They may be leading projects, publishing seminal papers, or collaborating widely, thereby shaping both the theory and practice of Living Labs.

Different centrality types reflect different kinds of impact. “Popular” authors may collaborate widely without influencing the broader network, while “Influential” or “Connector” authors, though less prolific, can shape the field through strategic or bridging roles. Connector authors like Mulder, Puerari, and Loorbach are essential for linking thematic or methodological clusters, helping to integrate the field and promote cross-pollination of ideas.

Overall, the table underscores that a handful of authors play key roles in driving the Living Lab field. Some are recognized broadly for their prolific collaborations, some shape the network’s intellectual currents, and others connect diverse clusters or disciplines. Collectively, these authors act as pillars of the Living Lab research community, influencing how knowledge is produced, disseminated, and integrated.

The co-authorship network analysis does more than reveal collaboration patterns; it also highlights the conceptual DNA of the Living Lab field. Authors like Schaffers, Ballon, Katzy, and Pallot anchor the ICT and innovation management tradition, positioning Living Labs as infrastructures for experimentation. Mulder, Schuurman, and Lievens bring in design thinking and co-creation methodologies, grounding the participatory dimension of the field. Bulkeley, Loorbach, Frantzeskaki, Raven, Puerari, and McCormick connect Living Labs to sustainability transitions and urban governance, framing them as vehicles for systemic change. Connector figures such as Mulder, Puerari, and Loorbach weave these strands together, enabling cross-pollination between innovation, design, and governance communities. Taken together, the table maps how Living Lab research has evolved at the intersection of technology, design, and sustainability, showing that its intellectual vitality stems from the integration of these diverse but complementary traditions.

However, while the presence of such champions provides stability and momentum, the maturation of the Living Labs' intellectual space cannot rest on a handful of actors alone. Sustained growth requires broader participation, more distributed collaborations, and the inclusion of diverse voices across disciplines, geographies, and practice communities. In this sense, the champions are essential for convening, setting standards, and connecting ideas, but the vitality of the field depends on the collective engagement of the wider research community, ensuring that Living Labs evolve into a truly integrative and resilient knowledge domain.

This calls for deliberate strategies by funders, institutions, and networks to expand participation and strengthen ties beyond the current champions.

Conclusions & Implications

This study set out to map the intellectual architecture of Living Lab research, examining co-authorship networks to identify structural patterns, key actors, and conceptual clusters. The results reveal a field that is both anchored and fragmented: anchored by a handful of highly central authors and clusters that provide stability and continuity yet fragmented across distinct traditions that remain only partially connected.

At the structural level, the analysis highlighted several recurring champions, such as Schaffers, Bulkeley, Schuurman, Frantzeskaki, and Leminen, who play crucial roles as popular collaborators, influential centers of gravity, and connectors bridging otherwise disparate groups. These individuals and their teams function as the stabilizing pillars of

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the field, ensuring that Living Lab research has both intellectual momentum and practical visibility. Their repeated appearance across different measures of centrality underlines their role in setting agendas, advancing methodologies, and linking diverse perspectives.

At the conceptual level, the co-authorship clusters point to the "DNA" of Living Lab scholarship. One cluster traces back to sustainability transitions and urban governance (Bulkeley, Frantzeskaki, Raven), another to ICT-driven European innovation projects (Schaffers, Komninos, Pallot), a third to methodological development and intermediary roles (Schuurman, Ballon, Marez), and yet another to business and management perspectives (Leminen, Westerlund, Nystrom). These distinct but overlapping intellectual lineages underscore the interdisciplinary nature of the field and its positioning at the crossroads of technology, governance, sustainability, and management.

From a network-theoretical perspective, the current shape of the field combines resilience and fragility. Its resilience comes from redundancy at the core: multiple champions ensure that knowledge does not depend on a single hub. Yet fragility remains, since much of the network's coherence rests on a small group of highly central actors. A more distributed pattern of centrality, where mid-range and emerging scholars also build cross-cluster ties, would strengthen redundancy, expand resilience, and enhance the adaptive capacity of the field.

The implications are clear: while strong champions remain essential for convening, standard-setting, and anchoring the field, the long-term vitality of Living Lab research depends on cultivating a broader and more distributed base of participation. This requires not only increasing the number of collaborations, but also intentionally diversifying who collaborates with whom. Fostering distributed collaborations means creating opportunities for early-career researchers, practitioners, and voices from underrepresented regions to engage meaningfully in shaping the research agenda. It also involves bridging disciplinary silos, where sustainability scholars, innovation researchers, ICT developers, and governance experts engage in sustained dialogue rather than parallel conversations.

Funders, institutions, and scholarly networks can play a decisive role in this transition. Targeted funding calls that reward cross-disciplinary and cross-national consortia, platforms that facilitate knowledge exchange between academic and practice communities, and recognition structures that value collaborative over individual achievements are all mechanisms that can strengthen the connective tissue of the field. Importantly, these efforts should not only expand participation horizontally, across

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geographies and thematic areas, but also vertically, by integrating different levels of expertise, from theoretical development to applied experimentation.

Adopting such strategies will help Living Lab research move from a field organized around a few central figures into a resilient, integrative, and adaptive knowledge domain. This shift is critical if the field is to keep pace with the complexity of the societal challenges it seeks to address climate transition, urban sustainability, digital innovation, and inclusive governance. Just as Living Labs themselves embody co-creation and distributed intelligence in practice, the research community should also embody these principles in its intellectual architecture. These moves will strengthen Living Labs into a robust knowledge ecosystem, capable of continuously adapting, expanding, and delivering insights that matter across contexts.

What is at stake is not only the intellectual coherence of an academic field, but the societal capacity of Living Labs to act as adaptive, cross-sector innovation systems. At their best, Living Labs enable governments, firms, civil society, and citizens to work together on challenges that no single sector can solve in isolation – climate resilience, digital transformation, social inclusion, etc. However, for this potential to be realized, funders, governments, and research institutions have a decisive role to play by supporting distributed collaborations, rewarding cross-sector and cross-border partnerships, and creating infrastructures for knowledge circulation. By doing this they can help Living Labs evolve into resilient, integrative systems of innovation. The future vitality of the field depends on these choices. Institutions have a responsibility to create the infrastructures (shared data platforms, joint training programs, integrative funding calls) that allow knowledge and practice to circulate, recombine, and evolve.

Funders, whether national, European, or philanthropic, can design integrative funding calls that reward cross-sector partnerships and invest in durable infrastructures rather than one-off projects. Governments and policymakers can embed Living Labs into policy cycles, using them as experimental spaces for regulatory innovation, smart city initiatives, and sustainability transitions, while also lowering structural barriers to collaboration. Universities and research institutions can foster the next generation of Living Lab practitioners by creating joint training programs, interdisciplinary graduate tracks, and recognition systems that value co-produced knowledge alongside traditional outputs. Cities and local authorities, as conveners of diverse communities, can provide not only physical and digital spaces, but also open data platforms that enable collective experimentation. The private sector brings essential resources, expertise, and scaling capacity, but must engage as co-learners committed to shared value creation rather than

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narrow corporate pilots. Civil society organizations and citizen groups ensure that Living Labs remain legitimate, inclusive, and grounded in lived experience, strengthening trust and accountability. Finally, international networks such as ENoLL, OECD platforms, and EU missions play an indispensable role as bridges and translators, connecting national efforts into a global learning system that avoids duplication and accelerates collective progress.

Taken together, these contributions highlight that the vitality of Living Labs depends on shared responsibility across the quadruple and quintuple helix. Only through this distributed commitment can Living Labs evolve from scattered projects into enduring infrastructures for collective problem-solving.

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